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Heatwave impacts on intertidal seagrass reflectance: from laboratory experiment to satellite mapping of seagrass heat shock index

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ABSTRACT

Seagrasses play a vital role in coastal ecosystems, providing habitat, stabilising sediments, and contributing to carbon sequestration. However, global warming has increased the frequency and intensity of heatwaves, posing a significant threat to seagrass health. This study investigates the effects of marine and atmospheric heatwaves on the spectral reflectance of the intertidal seagrass *Zostera noltii*. Laboratory experiments were conducted under controlled heatwave conditions, where hyperspectral reflectance measurements were taken to assess the impacts over time. Simulated heatwave conditions caused a substantial decline in seagrass reflectance, particularly in the green and near-infrared regions, corresponding to the darkening of green leaves. Key vegetation indices, including the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) and Green Leaf Index (GLI), showed pronounced reductions under heatwave stress, with NDVI values decreasing by up to 34% and GLI by 57%. A novel metric, the Seagrass Heat Shock Index (SHSI), was developed to quantify the transition of seagrass leaves from green to brown, demonstrating a stronger ability to capture the effects of heatwave exposure on seagrass colouration. Multispectral satellite observations corroborated the laboratory results, revealing widespread darkening of seagrass leaves during marine and atmospheric heatwave events in South Brittany, France. Notably, darkened seagrass patches were observed in intertidal areas exposed to air temperatures exceeding 32 °C for over 13.5 h per day. These findings highlight the potential of spectral reflectance as a tool for detecting early signs of heatwave-induced stress in seagrasses, offering a valuable method for remote sensing-based habitat assessment. The present study underscores the potential of remote sensing to capture rapid environmental changes in intertidal zones, enabling for continuous monitoring of seagrass meadows under the current and future climate regimes.

1. Introduction

Seagrasses play a crucial role in coastal ecosystems by providing habitats and feeding grounds for various marine species, supporting marine biodiversity, and contributing to primary production and carbon sequestration (Sousa et al., 2019; Unsworth et al., 2022). Seagrasses are essential for several ecological functions, such as sediment stabilisation (Infantes et al., 2022) or eutrophication mitigation by consuming

nutrients (Gladstone-Gallagher et al., 2018). This justifies their use as indicators of environmental changes due to their sensitivity to water quality variations (Zoffoli et al., 2021). The interactions between seagrass meadows and their associated herbivores further enhance the delivery of ecosystem services, including coastal protection, fisheries support and provision of habitat and resources for birds (Gardner and Finlayson, 2018; Jankowska et al., 2019; Unsworth and Butterworth, 2021; Zoffoli et al., 2023). Understanding their ecological role and

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preserving seagrasses is vital for maintaining the biodiversity and productivity of coastal regions (Ramesh and Mohanraju, 2020; Scott et al., 2018).

Despite their crucial role in marine ecosystems, seagrasses face numerous threats that compromise their health and functionality. Intertidal seagrasses are subjected to a combination of aquatic and aerial abiotic conditions (e.g. salinity, wave actions, sun irradiance, air temperature, desiccation) linked with tidal cycles, and face disturbance from terrestrial and aquatic stressors. Human activities such as coastal development are primary threats, reducing the available habitat for seagrasses and increasing water turbidity, limiting light penetration and photosynthesis (Waycott et al., 2009). Seagrasses are also threatened by runoff from agricultural fields and urban areas leading to nutrient enrichment. Eutrophication promotes the growth of seaweed in coastal waters, causing macroalgal blooms that compete with seagrasses for light and nutrients (Brun et al., 2003; Oiry et al., 2024; Thomsen et al., 2023). Pollution from industrial and agricultural sources introduces harmful chemicals and heavy metals into coastal waters, posing toxic risks to seagrass health (Bastos et al., 2023; Green et al., 2021; Zahoor and Mushtaq, 2023). Among the manifold anthropogenic stressors, heatwaves (HWs), exacerbated by climate change, pose a severe threat to seagrasses, with catastrophic dieback events observed worldwide (Carlson et al., 2018; Marbà and Duarte, 2010; Moore and Jarvis, 2008; Strydom et al., 2020; Thomson et al., 2015).

Marine Heatwaves (MHWs) are defined by Hobday et al. (2016) as prolonged discrete anomalously warm water events, while Atmospheric Heatwaves (AHWs) are defined by Perkins and Alexander (2013) as periods of at least three consecutive days with temperatures exceeding the 90th percentile of a time series covering at least 30 years. Subtidal seagrass meadows are exposed to MHWs, whereas at the interface between land and ocean, intertidal seagrasses are exposed to both MHWs and AHWs. Both HWs profoundly impact seagrass physiology, with effects varying between species and geographic location. Widespread seagrass species such as *Zostera marina* exhibit high susceptibility to elevated sea surface temperatures during winter and spring, leading to advanced flowering, high mortality rates, and reduced biomass (Sawall et al., 2021). Similarly, *Cymodocea nodosa* shows increased photosynthetic activity during HWs but suffers negative effects on photosynthetic performance and leaf biomass during recovery (Deguette et al., 2022). Additionally, different populations of *Zostera marina* along the European thermal gradient exhibit varied photophysiological responses during the recovery phase of HWs, indicating differential adaptation capabilities among populations (Winters et al., 2011). High-latitude populations exhibited prolonged declines in photophysiological performance even after temperatures returned to control levels, whereas the low-latitude Adriatic population showed full recovery (Winters et al., 2011). These events intensify other stressors, such as overgrazing and seed burial, compromising recruitment (Guerrero-Meseguer et al., 2020). Although extensive research exists on marine heatwaves' effects on subtidal seagrasses (Arias-Ortiz et al., 2018; Deguette et al., 2022; Strydom et al., 2020), less attention has been given to intertidal habitats and even less to the effect of atmospheric extreme events on intertidal seagrasses. Nonetheless, recent research showed that the low tide exposure of *Zostera noltii* to a simulated four-day atmospheric HW caused significant decreases in its photosynthetic efficiency, resulting in leaf darkening and decay (Román et al., 2023).

The increased occurrence of extreme climate events calls for the implementation of monitoring strategies able to provide detailed and spatially explicit assessments of HWs' effects on seagrass meadows. In such a context, remote sensing, whose ability to map seagrass distribution over a variety of spatio-temporal scales has been demonstrated (Davies et al., 2024a, 2024b; Oiry et al., 2024; Román et al., 2021), proved useful to study the changes in seagrass coverage caused by extreme HW events (Strydom et al., 2020). The pigment composition of plants, including chlorophylls, carotenoids, and anthocyanins, significantly influences their spectral signature in the visible range due to their

specific light absorption properties (Davies et al., 2023; Douay et al., 2022; Olmedo-Masat et al., 2020; Ustin and Jacquemoud, 2020). During the senescence phase of seagrass' life-cycle, the degradation of chlorophyll and accessory pigments results in noticeable changes in leaf colouration and reflectance, including increased reflectance in the red and green wavelengths and shifts in the red-edge position (Boyer et al., 1988; Mariën et al., 2019; Peñuelas et al., 2004). Leaf darkening, often observed after stress events, produces reflectance changes similar to those caused by senescence, enabling the detection of vegetation stress through remote sensing (Boyer et al., 1988; Peñuelas et al., 2004). Spectral indices such as the Brown Pigment Index (BPI) and the Photochemical Reflectance Index (PRI) have been developed to assess changes in the physiological status of terrestrial plants, particularly under oxidative and drought stress (Garbulsky et al., 2011; Skendzic, 2023). Like terrestrial vegetation, seagrasses share a comparable pigment composition dominated by chlorophylls, carotenoids, and xanthophylls (Peñuelas et al., 2004), suggesting that similar optical responses to stress could be expected. However, this relationship has not yet been fully demonstrated for intertidal seagrasses, where environmental conditions such as periodic emersion and water optical effects may modify the expression of these pigment-related spectral features.

This study aims to experimentally test the hypothesis that HWs alter the reflectance of the intertidal seagrass *Zostera noltii*. Controlled experiments in intertidal chambers were conducted to evaluate the direct impact of heat stress on seagrass reflectance. The findings were then applied to satellite remote sensing images, providing critical insights into the spatial extent and temporal dynamics of HW effects on seagrass meadows. By linking experimental results with large-scale observations of seagrass leaves' darkening, the study aimed at underscoring the potential of remote sensing to enhance our understanding of seagrass responses to extreme thermal events across diverse settings and timescales.

2. Materials & methods

2.1. Laboratory experiment

2.1.1. Sampling and acclimation of seagrasses

Seagrass samples were taken in summer 2024, at low tide, from a *Zostera noltii* (dwarf eelgrass) meadow located in Bourgneuf Bay, France (46°57'32.0"N, 2°10'37.0"W). A rectangular metal coring device was used to sample seagrass from an area of 30 cm × 15 cm × 5 cm (length x width x depth, respectively), maintaining the sediment structure and avoiding damage to seagrass rhizomes and leaves (Fig. 1 A). This coring device enabled consistent sediment sampling depth, minimising variability between samples. A total of six samples were collected. Samples including seagrass, sediment, meiofauna, and macrofauna were placed in plastic trays. Maintaining the entire biota allowed for natural interactions between components and reduced stress on the seagrass. Seawater was added to each tray to avoid desiccation during transportation to the laboratory (1 h drive). Simultaneously, seawater was sampled 4 km away from the seagrass sampling site and transported to the laboratory, where it was filtered using a 0.22 µm nitrocellulose filter to remove suspended particulate matter. The filtered seawater was used in the acclimation tank and the intertidal chambers. The seagrasses were acclimated for one week with a water temperature of 17 °C, matching the in situ temperature during sampling. Salinity was regularly monitored during the acclimation phases using a refractometer, and any evaporation losses were compensated with distilled water. During the acclimation phase, seagrasses were maintained under a constant photosynthetically active radiation Photosynthetically Active Radiation (PAR) of 150 µmol m⁻² s⁻¹, corresponding to the maximum light intensity provided by the experimental intertidal chambers. This setup ensured that samples were pre-adapted to the same irradiance conditions used during the heatwave experiment, thereby preventing any confounding effects related to light reduction upon transfer to the

Fig. 1. Illustration of the experiment. A: Seagrass field sampling using a coring device; B: Intertidal chamber used during the experiment; C: Seagrass sample inside a chamber during the experiment at high tide; D: Treatment sample at the start of the experiment; E: Treatment sample at the end of the experiment, 3 days after the start of the HW event.

chambers.

2.1.2. Experimental design

A tidal cycle (i.e. regularly alternating 6 h of low-tide and 6 h of high-tide) was simulated in the laboratory using an intertidal chamber system from ElectricBlue® (Fig. 1B; Electric Blue, 2023). The experimental setup allowed only two tidal states: high tide or low tide, with no intermediate stages. The transition between these states took about 15 min to complete after initiation. During the phase of high tide, a volume of 30 L of filtered seawater was pumped and circulated through the chamber (Fig. 1B, C). During low tide, the seagrass sample was emerged.

The six acclimated rectangular seagrass samples were split into two subsets and placed in two independent chambers used in parallel, with one chamber used for control and the other for the experimental treatment. The intertidal chambers were equipped with LED lights that emitted a low amount of red and infrared radiation. To achieve a PAR intensity of up to $150 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$, a filament bulb was added inside the chambers. During the diurnal phase of the experiment, the PAR was kept constant in both intertidal chambers. To follow the circadian cycle, these lights (both LED and filament bulb) were turned on and off each day, at the time of natural sunrise and sunset, respectively.

Air temperature and water temperature were controlled inside the experiment chambers to reproduce the range of variability observed in the field (Fig. 2). Field temperature was measured using in situ sensors (T7.3 EnvLoggers from ElectricBlue®) deployed at the sampling site in August 2024. The loggers were positioned along a transect from the upper to the lower intertidal zone, attached to pre-existing wooden poles at the sediment surface. In complement, the daily temperature maxima recorded in situ were compared with measurements from the nearest Météo France weather station (Fig. A1, Section 6.1). The control chamber was kept at temperatures representing typical summer conditions, with water temperatures at 18°C and air temperatures from 19°C to 23°C , following natural daily temperature fluctuations (Fig. 2 A). In the treatment chamber, the air temperature was adjusted to mimic an AHW that affected the seagrass meadow in Quiberon, South Brittany, France ($47^\circ35'40.0''\text{N}$, $3^\circ07'30.0''\text{W}$), from September 2 to September 6, 2021. Air temperature in the experimental chamber was set to vary from 23°C (at night) to 35°C (daytime) during the first day of the experiment, and increase by 1°C daily during three consecutive days. Water temperature in the experimental chamber was also adjusted to mimic MHW conditions, starting at the seasonal baseline (18°C) and rising incrementally by 0.5°C daily to simulate the increasing temperatures during the event. This aimed to reproduce the thermal stress experienced by the seagrass meadow during the MHW of Quiberon, France in September 2021 (Fig. 2 B). The experiment, with both treatment and control chambers, was repeated three times with the rectangular seagrass subsets to obtain replicates (hereafter referred to as “Run”).

2.1.3. Optical measurements

2.1.3.1. Hyperspectral reflectance measurements. Throughout the experiment, the hyperspectral reflectance, $R(\lambda)$, of both the control and

Fig. 2. Temperature variation in the control (A) and treatment (B) intertidal chambers, during the HW experiment. The red line indicates air temperature, and the blue line water temperature. Due to the tidal cycle of immersion / emersion, the seagrasses experienced the temperatures represented by solid lines. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

treatment seagrasses was measured using an ASD HandHeld 2 equipped with a fibre optic extension placed inside the chamber. The measurement set up made it possible to automatically acquire $R(\lambda)$ without opening the chamber. An average of five $R(\lambda)$ spectra, each with an integration time of 544 ms, was taken every minute during daytime (Malvern Panalytical, 2023). Every 10 min, the fibre optic was switched from one intertidal chamber to the other to measure $R(\lambda)$ in both the treatment and control. The reflectance calibration was performed each morning at the very first moment of low tide using a Spectralon white reference with 99% Lambertian reflectivity.

2.1.3.2. Spectrum post-processing. A Savitzky–Golay smoothing filter with a 5 nm moving window was applied to each spectrum using the *hdsar* package in R (Lehnert et al., 2019), to reduce instrumental noise while preserving key pigment absorption features. The second derivative at 665 nm ($\delta\delta 665$), showing the highest variability between the control and the treatment, was tested as an indicator of the spectral changes following HWs.

The effect the HW on $R(\lambda)$ was also quantified using two radiometric indices:

- The Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI, Rouse et al. (1974)), a proxy of chlorophyll-a concentration (Eq. 1)

$$NDVI = \frac{R(840) - R(668)}{R(840) + R(668)} \quad (1)$$

where $R(840)$ and $R(668)$ are the reflectance at 840 and 668 nm respectively.

- The Green Leaf Index (GLI, Louhaichi et al., 2001), a quantification of the seagrass leaves greenness (Eq. 2)

$$GLI = \frac{[R(550) - R(668)] + [R(550) - R(450)]}{(2 \times R(550)) + R(668) + R(450)} \quad (2)$$

where $R(550)$ and $R(450)$ are the reflectance in the green (at 550 nm) and in the blue (at 450 nm) spectral bands, respectively.

To quantify heatwave-induced alterations in seagrass reflectance, we developed the Seagrass Heat Shock Index (SHSI). This metric captures deviations in reflectance around 560 and 740 nm—corresponding to the green-yellow and red-edge spectral regions—where the differences between impacted and unimpacted seagrasses are most pronounced (Fig. 7).

Because the SHSI is designed to detect changes in spectral shape rather than absolute reflectance values, the reflectance spectrum of each individual sample must first be standardised using a min–max transformation (Eq. 3; Cao et al., 2017)

$$R_i^*(\lambda) = \frac{R_i(\lambda) - \min(R_i)}{\max(R_i) - \min(R_i)} \quad (3)$$

The standardised reflectance values R^* at 560 nm and 740 nm are then compared to a linear baseline defined between two anchor wavelengths: 490 nm (blue region) and 865 nm (near-infrared). The blue anchor (490 nm) was selected because impacted and non-impacted seagrasses exhibit nearly identical standardised reflectance in this region, providing a stable reference point. The near-infrared (NIR) anchor (865 nm) was chosen as the endpoint because both spectra converge at longer wavelengths, making it an optimal reference for multispectral sensors such as Sentinel-2 (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Calculation of the Seagrass Heat Shock Index (SHSI) for impacted (A) and unimpacted (B) seagrass leaves. The orange line shows the reflectance interpolation between 490 nm and 865 nm, while the red dashed vertical lines at 560 nm and 740 nm indicate the two line heights that are summed to obtain the SHSI value (Eq. 4). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

$$\text{SHSI} = \text{LH}(\lambda_{\text{green}}) + \text{LH}(\lambda_{\text{RE}})$$

$$\text{LH}(\lambda_i) = R^*(\lambda_1) + \frac{\lambda_i - \lambda_1}{\lambda_2 - \lambda_1} [R^*(\lambda_2) - R^*(\lambda_1)] - R^*(\lambda_i) \quad (4)$$

where R^* is the min-max standardized reflectance (Eq. 3) and LH is the line height between the measured and interpolated reflectance. Four wavelengths are used to compute the SHSI: $\lambda_1 = 490$ nm, $\lambda_2 = 865$ nm, $\lambda_{\text{green}} = 560$ nm, and $\lambda_{\text{RE}} = 740$ nm. By definition, the SHSI is mathematically constrained between -2 and $+2$, although these extreme values cannot be reached under natural conditions. A positive SHSI indicates darkened seagrass, whereas a negative SHSI characterises green vegetation. These specific wavelengths were selected to match the spectral configuration of current and upcoming multispectral satellite missions (e.g., Sentinel-2, Landsat Next), ensuring broad applicability for remote sensing analyses. Because NIR radiations are strongly absorbed by water, the SHSI can be reliably computed only for emerged seagrasses during low-tide conditions.

2.2. Validation of the SHSI

A field campaign was conducted in the seagrass meadow of the Ria de Aveiro Coastal Lagoon (Portugal) from July 14 to 18, 2025. Two distinct study areas were selected, and within each, a grid sampling with additional random sampling stations was established, covering a total surface of 5.6 ha (Fig. 4). Grid sampling with added random sampling is optimal for detecting abundance changes and mapping benthic organisms (Bijleveld et al., 2012). At every station, a Quadrat Point (QP) was collected as georeferenced quadrat images across the meadow. Each image was subsequently analysed in the laboratory by independent

observers, who classified the meadow condition as either impacted by heat stress (i.e., leaves showing visible discolouration or darkening) or unimpacted (i.e., leaves appearing green). This set of visual classifications was used as the ground-truth dataset.

2.2.1. Satellite observations of ria de Aveiro coastal lagoon, Portugal

To complement the in situ observations, a Level-2 Sentinel-2 MSI image acquired just one day after field sampling, on the 15th of July 2025 was downloaded from the Copernicus Open Access Hub (European Space Agency, 2024a), provided by the European Space Agency (ESA). Level-2 products correspond to atmospherically corrected surface reflectance (Sen2Cor processor; European Space Agency, 2024b) and are delivered as orthorectified data at a spatial resolution of 10–20 m. SHSI was computed using Eq. 4.

Because the ground-truth dataset consists of georeferenced points classified into two categories (i.e., impacted or unimpacted), the continuous SHSI values were subsequently categorised as follows:

- SHSI >0: Impacted.
- SHSI <0: Unimpacted.

2.2.2. Validation metrics

This binary classification derived from the satellite data was compared against the ground-truth labels obtained from the photo-quadrats. A confusion matrix was computed, from which standard performance metrics (overall accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, user and producer accuracies, F1-score, and Cohen's κ) were derived to assess the reliability of Sentinel-2-based SHSI in detecting heat-stressed seagrass patches.

Fig. 4. Location of field observations in a seagrass meadow impacted by a HW that occurred on the 14th of July 2025 in Ria de Aveiro coastal lagoon, Portugal. Green dots indicate the location of QPs over unimpacted seagrasses (i.e. showing a green colour on the field), and orange dots indicate the location of QPs taken over impacted seagrasses (i.e. showing a brown colour on the field). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

2.3. Focus on a study site: Seagrass meadow of Quiberon, France

Field measurements were taken on the 10th of September 2021 after an atmospheric and marine HW to assess the impact of heat stress on seagrass. The study site was a seagrass meadow near Quiberon (France : 46°57'32.0"N, 2°10'37.0"W, Fig. 5). Impacted brown seagrass leaves were observed over large patches of the meadow alongside areas covered by unimpacted green seagrass (Fig. 6). A total of 96 QPs were collected. These images allowed for visual assessment of vegetation type, density, and colouration. The QPs were then divided into two categories: green seagrasses (henceforth: unimpacted QPs) and brown seagrasses (henceforth: impacted QPs), based on a visual estimation of the leaf colouration (Fig. 5).

2.3.1. Temperature data and HW detection

2.3.1.1. Air temperature. Hourly air temperature data from 1952 to 2024 (more than 395,000 observations) from a nearby weather station (Lorient-Lann Bihoué, 47°45'46"N 3°26'11"W) were retrieved from Météo-France (<https://portail-api.meteofrance.fr>).

2.3.1.2. Water temperature. Sea Surface Temperature (SST) data from 1982 to 2022 over the Quiberon coastal area were downloaded from the Copernicus Marine Service (CMEMS, 2024) portal. The product provides

Fig. 6. Illustration of the two colourations of seagrass leaves observed in situ on the 10th of September 2021 after a heatwave in Quiberon, South Brittany (France). A: Picture of a zone with both green and brown seagrass; B: Seagrass quadrat with green leaves; C: Seagrass quadrat with brown leaves; D: Picture of a zone where all leaves turned brown. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

daily SST at a spatial resolution of $0.05^\circ \times 0.05^\circ$. An area of 2700 km² was extracted and daily averages over this area were computed. This area was large enough to minimise missing values caused by cloud cover while remaining small enough to limit the influence of offshore SST stability.

2.3.1.3. Heatwave detection and characterization. MHW and AHW detection was performed using the HeatwaveR package in R (Schlegel and Smit, 2018). This package utilises the methodology proposed by Hobday et al. (2016) to detect HW events. The annual climatology (i.e. the average temperature of each day of the year since the start of the time series) of both air and water temperature was computed. HWs were defined as events when the temperature exceeded the 90th percentile of the climatology during three consecutive days. Furthermore, the severity of each event was assessed using the methodology proposed by Hobday et al. (2018).

2.3.2. Satellite observations of Quiberon

Three 2021 Sentinel-2 images of the study site were selected during low tide to assess the effect of the combined AHW and MHW (“HW event”, henceforth) on the seagrass meadow: the first image was taken 5 days before the HW (1st of September 2021), the second image during the HW (6th of September 2021) and the third image one month later (8th of October 2021; due to tidal and cloud cover constraints, no images closer to the HW event were usable.). Level-2 data were downloaded from the Copernicus Open Access Hub.

The SHSI (Eq. 4) was computed and mapped for each image. For the pixel containing a field QP (Fig. 5), the satellite-derived reflectance was extracted, and compared before and after the HW event.

2.3.3. Emersion time of the seagrass meadow

The spatial distribution of seagrass emersion time during low tide was estimated using bathymetric and water level data. Very high-resolution bathymetric data (Litto3D® product) for the Quiberon intertidal meadow were sourced from the “Service Hydrographique et Océanographique de la Marine” (SHOM, 2021), while one-minute interval water level data were downloaded from the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission data portal (IOC, 2024), using measurements from the nearest tide gauge at Le Croüesty. A 2.85 m vertical correction was applied to the Litto3D data to align its zero reference with that of the water level data (RAM, SHOM, 2022).

Fig. 5. Location of QPs in a seagrass meadow impacted by an HW that occurred on the 10th of September 2021 in Quiberon, South Brittany, France. The red line indicates the intertidal zone (zone between high tide and low tide, exposed during low tide), the dark green area indicates the extent of the seagrass meadow and the olive area indicates saltmarshes. Green dots indicate the location of QPs over unimpacted seagrasses (i.e. showing a green colour on the field), and orange dots indicate the location of QPs taken over impacted seagrasses (i.e. showing a brown colour on the field). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Once aligned, the corrected elevation was compared to water height for each pixel and each time step during the HW event. The emersion time was then calculated as the daily total time each pixel remained exposed over the duration of the AHW.

2.4. Statistics

Generalised Linear Models (GLMs) were used to assess relative differences over time in response variables (Spectral Indices) with different treatments (Impacted vs Unimpacted). To analyse the effect of HW on the reflectance indices observed during the lab experiment, the relative change was modelled as a function of Days (1–3: Discrete) with Runs (1–3: Factor) and Timestep within Run (1–6: Factor) as cross-random factors. Satellite-derived SHSI was modelled as a function of Date (1–3: Discrete) and Treatment (Impacted vs Unimpacted: Categorical). A Generalised Additive Model (GAM) was used to assess the relationship between relative SHSI change as a function of emersion time. SHSI was modelled as a function of emersion time with a basis spline. All model parameters were estimated within a Bayesian framework using the “brms” and “RStan” packages in R to leverage the Stan language (Bürkner, 2021; Carpenter et al., 2017; R Core Team, 2025; Stan Development Team, C, 2020). The response variables were modelled assuming a Gaussian distribution, with weakly informative priors (Student-T(3,0,2.5)). Model parameters were estimated using Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) sampling, with four chains of 5000 iterations and a warm-up of 500.

3. Results

3.1. Laboratory experiment

3.1.1. Heatwave effect on seagrass reflectance

During the laboratory HW experiment, the seagrass reflectance was drastically impacted by the increase in both air and water temperature (Fig. 7). The Control $R(\lambda)$ displayed a spectral shape typical of seagrass, with a green peak around 560 nm, a valley associated with chlorophyll-a absorption around 665 nm, and a high NIR plateau beyond 705 nm. This remained stable over time, with only minimal changes in magnitude and spectral features. In contrast, the Treatment $R(\lambda)$ showed severe changes throughout the experiment. During day 1, the Treatment $R(\lambda)$ was generally similar to the Control $R(\lambda)$, despite a slightly less marked peak around 560 nm and slightly lower Red-Edge around 750 nm. A drastic decrease was then observed during days 2 and 3 across all wavelengths, particularly in the green–yellow spectral region (500–650 nm) and in the red-edge and short-wave portion of the NIR (710–910 nm). During

day 3, the collapse in $R(\lambda)$ appeared to stabilise in the Red Edge and the shortwave NIR, whereas it slightly continued in the green spectral region. At the end of the HW experiment, the $R(\lambda)$ valley around 665 nm was also less pronounced, suggesting a decrease in chlorophyll-a concentration.

3.1.2. Heatwave effect on radiometric indices

All radiometric indices, $R'_{665\text{ nm}}$, NDVI, GLI and SHSI changed after the experimental heatwave (Fig. 8; Section 6.2).

At the start of the experiment (day 1), the difference between Treatment and Control was not significant in $R'_{665\text{ nm}}$, NDVI and GLI (Fig. 8 A, B & C). During days 2 and 3 the radiometric indices all decreased significantly, with an overall decline of 68%, 31% and 54 for $R'_{665\text{ nm}}$, NDVI and GLI.

Unlike the other metrics, the SHSI of the Treatment was on average 35% lower than that of the Control in day 1 (Fig. 8 D). By day 2, the SHSI exhibited a rapid increase of approximately 66%, eventually reaching an overall rise of 168% by day 3.

With a maximum deviation of 168%, SHSI emerged as the most sensitive index for detecting seagrass darkening. Consequently, only this index was considered for the next steps of the study.

Looking at raw SHSI values revealed clear distinctions between the Control and Treatment groups (Fig. 9 A). On day 1, the SHSI of the Control and Treatment groups were comparable, with median values of -0.25 and -0.23 , respectively. By the end of the experiment, seagrasses in the Treatment group exhibited a median SHSI of 0.09, consistent with their visibly darkened appearance. In contrast, the Control group retained a green appearance throughout the experiment, with a median SHSI of -0.12 . A negative SHSI was considered indicative of non-impacted seagrasses, while a positive SHSI was used as a marker for impacted seagrasses.

3.2. Validation in ria de Aveiro coastal lagoon, Portugal

The two sites of the Ria de Aveiro Lagoon exhibited contrasting responses to heat stress (Fig. 10). Site A showed extensive areas of darkened seagrass, with large portions of the meadow displaying positive SHSI values (Fig. 10A). At this site, most QPs corresponded to visibly browned seagrass leaves (Fig. 10C). In contrast, Site B appeared largely unaffected, with seagrass maintaining a green colouration and negative SHSI values across most of the area (Fig. 10B & D).

Overall the SHSI can detect impacted meadow with an accuracy of 0.92, a kappa coefficient of 0.84 and an F1 score of 0.92. The SHSI correctly identified all observed impacted pixels, but 19% of truly unimpacted pixels have shown positive SHSI (Table 1).

Fig. 7. Standardised hyperspectral reflectance of *Z. noltii* leaves during the HW experiment, showing the Control (Left) and Treatment (Right) measurements. The colour indicates the progression along the experiment from the beginning (Day 1: Green), middle (Day 2: Yellow) and end (Day 3: Brown). A min-max standardisation was applied to each individual spectrum. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 8. Comparison of spectral metrics for detecting reflectance changes of seagrass leaves after a HW. A: Relative difference between the Treatment and the Control over time for A) the second derivative at 665 nm B) the NDVI C) the GLI and D) the SHSI. Points indicate raw data, the line represents a GLM estimate, while the shaded area is the model's 89% confidence interval. The dashed lines represent no difference between the Control and the Treatment.

3.3. HW of September 2021 in Quiberon, South Brittany

3.3.1. Spectral changes

Sentinel-2 images acquired on the 1st and 6th of September 2021 were analysed to assess the short-term impact of an HW on seagrass leaves in South Brittany, France (Fig. 11A and C). Both an AHW and a MHW occurred during the 2021 summer, from the 4th to the 7th and from the 3rd to the 8th of September, respectively (Fig. 11B). Within just a few days, the temperature experienced a sharp increase, from 22.2 to 30.8 °C in air, and from 17.7 to 19.3 °C in water. During this period, the 90th percentile of the air temperatures was 25.3 °C and 18.8 °C for the water temperature. The air temperature anomaly of 9.9 °C classified the AHW as a strong event, whereas the 1.7 °C anomaly in water temperature classified the MHW as a moderate event.

Two days after the start of the AHW, the Sentinel-2 image from the 6th of September revealed patches of brown seagrass in the true-colour composition (Fig. 11C). Such brown patches were absent from the image on the 1st of September, taken before the HW began (Fig. 11A). Before the HW, all QPs appeared green on the Sentinel-2 image, with similar reflectance spectra, typical of green seagrass leaves (Fig. 11A and D). Their reflectance spectra showed a peak at 560 nm (in the green part of the spectrum), low values at 665 nm and a high NIR plateau (> 705 nm). However, on the 6th of September, QPs classified as impacted during the field campaign, showed significant differences in their reflectance spectral shape compared to unimpacted QPs (Fig. 11C and E). The

reflectance spectra of brown seagrass were characterised by the loss of the reflectance peak at 560 nm and a decrease in the NIR plateau, which was replaced by a steadily increasing slope up to 940 nm. The darkening of large seagrass patches could also be observed in the true-colour composition (Fig. 11C).

3.3.2. SHSI metric applied to Sentinel-2

Using Sentinel-2 data and the QPs, SHSI of green seagrass areas that appeared unimpacted by the HW (Unimpacted QPs; Fig. 11C) remained negative between the 1st and the 6th of September 2021 (Fig. 9B). In contrast, seagrass impacted by the HW that turned brown (Impacted QPs; Fig. 11C) exhibited significant SHSI changes, with values becoming positive on the 6th of September (Fig. 9B). One month after the event, on the 8th of October 2021, the SHSI of unimpacted seagrass had remained negative. Regarding impacted seagrass, one month after the event, the SHSI decreased to values comparable to those of unimpacted seagrass.

Using the SHSI (Eq. 4), we detected large darkened seagrass patches in the meadow on 6th of September (Fig. 12). A total of 26.9 ha of seagrass turned brown between 1st and 6th of September. The largest brown patch covered nearly 8 ha. Overall, 24% of the total seagrass meadow area showed signs of darkening between 1st and 6th of September. Comparing the spatial distribution of darkened patches with the site's topography revealed that 94.6% of darkened areas were located above a bathymetric level of 3.9 m (Fig. 12, A and B). One month later, on 8th of October, the previously darkened areas appeared to have

Fig. 9. A - Median of the SHSI across experimental runs, on each day of the experiment. The error structure represents the 89% confidence interval. The green line shows values of the Control group while the orange line indicates values of the Treatment group. B - Changes in the SHSI estimated from Sentinel-2, before (1st of September 2021), during (6th of September 2021) and after (8th of October 2021) an HW in the seagrass meadow of Quiberon (South Brittany, France). The relative SHSI difference was calculated using the 1st of September as a reference. SHSI was calculated for two categories of Quadrat Points (QPs; Fig. 11): unimpacted seagrass (green) and impacted seagrass (orange). Points represent the estimated value of the SHSI using a GLM, while the error bars represent the 89% confidence interval. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 10. Sentinel-2 colour composition of the Seagrass Heat Shock Index over Site A (A) and Site B (B) of Ria de Aveiro Coastal Lagoon. Orange points represent QPs showing darkened seagrasses while green points represent QPs showing green seagrasses. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Table 1

Confusion matrix and accuracy metrics (Sensitivity, Specificity, User's and Producer's accuracy and F1 score) of the SHSI capacity to detect heat impacted-seagrasses.

		Observed			
		Unimpacted	Impacted		
Prediction		22	0		
	Unimpacted	5	38		
	Impacted				
Class	Sensitivity	Specificity	User's accuracy	Producer's accuracy	F1 Score
Unimpacted	0.81	1.00	1.00	0.81	0.90
Impacted	1.00	0.81	0.88	1.00	0.94

regained their green colouration (Fig. 12 C).

Additionally, there was a clear relationship between seagrass emergence time and seagrass darkening (Fig. 13; Section 6.3). Before the heatwave event, no clear relationship was observed between emergence time and SHSI values (Fig. 13A), with more than 98% of pixels exhibiting negative SHSI values. In contrast, during the heatwave, SHSI values increased sharply beyond an emergence duration of approximately 13 h 19 min per day (Fig. 13B). More than 88% of the pixels that were exposed for more than 13 h 19 min per day displayed positive SHSI values during the event.

4. Discussion

4.1. Effect of heatwaves on *Zostera noltii* reflectance

This study explored the dual effect of MHWs and AHWs on the spectral reflectance of intertidal seagrasses. Significant changes in seagrass reflectance exposed to HWs were observed both in field measurements and the laboratory experiment. The effects included a drop in reflectance around 560 and 740 nm (Fig. 8) as well as a drop in the second derivative at 665 nm ($R^2=665$), and in the NDVI, and GLI (Fig. 8A, B & C). By contrast, the SHSI showed a marked increase, reaching a maximum of 300% for some samples by day 3 (Fig. 8D), demonstrating its sensitivity to detect seagrass leaves darkening (Table 1). These changes suggest a progressive reduction in photosynthetic activity as well as potential structural or physiological changes to the leaves, such as degraded pigmentation, altered light absorption or lower water content. Moreover, we observed a considerable decrease in reflectance in the NIR region (700–900 nm) in stressed plants, which is likely related to the destruction of the membranes (chloroplasts, thylakoids, cell walls) due to thermal oxidative stress, and the consequent decrease of light scattering through the leaf surface (Knipling, 1970). The leaf darkening observed in plants subjected to thermal stress was mainly explained by the oxidation of phenolic compounds by the enzyme polyphenol oxidase and with damage to the photosynthetic apparatus (Allakhverdiev et al., 2008). High temperatures destabilise chloroplast membranes, disrupting photosystem II and impairing recovery of photosynthetic function.

Fig. 11. Intertidal seagrass meadow in South Brittany (France) observed before and during a heatwave (HW). A: RGB colour composition of the Sentinel-2 image of the 1st of September 2021 before the HW; C: RGB colour composition of the Sentinel-2 image of the 6th of September 2021 on the second day of a strong AHW. The circles correspond to QPs collected on the 10th of September 2021, with unimpacted seagrass in green and impacted seagrass in orange; B: Detection of HW events based on both Air Temperature and Sea Surface Temperature (SST). The solid line represents the daily average temperature, while the dashed line indicates the 90th percentile of the climatology. Coloured areas identify HWs (marine in blue and atmospheric in red). The two vertical dashed lines represent the acquisition dates of the two Sentinel-2 images (01-09-2021 and 06-09-2021); D: Sentinel-2 reflectance of seagrass leaves before the HW for both categories of QPs; E: Sentinel-2 reflectance of seagrass leaves during the HW for both categories of QPs. Average spectral signatures were obtained in areas where QPs corresponded to green and brown seagrass leaves (green and orange circles, respectively) as identified during the field survey. The shaded areas around the reflectance spectra represent the standard deviation. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

As chlorophyll-*a* degrades, the ratio of pigments shifts, with pigments like carotenoids becoming more prominent (Dascaluic et al., 2007; Jones and Clayton-Greene, 1992). These processes can eventually result in growth impairment and plant mortality.

The Seagrass Heat Shock Index (Eq. 4) developed in this study makes it possible to detect reductions in the green and the red-edge regions caused by thermal stress using only four reflectance bands (490, 560, 740 and 840 nm). These spectral bands (or close equivalents) are available in current (i.e. Sentinel-2, Pleiades-Neo, WorldView-3, SkySat, and GeoSat-2) and future multispectral missions (i.e. Sentinel-2 Next Generation and Landsat Next), opening new perspectives for the detection and monitoring of heatwave effects on intertidal seagrass. As shown in the next section, the SHSI can be used to assess the extent and severity of darkening events across intertidal seagrass meadows from high-resolution satellite images.

4.2. Satellite observations of HW effects on intertidal seagrass

Using our new Seagrass Heat Shock Index, Sentinel-2 images acquired before, during, and after a HW event made it possible to detect

seagrass leaf darkening at high spatial resolution, as well as to describe the spatial distribution of the heatwave impact over the whole meadow. The analysis of satellite images in Quiberon Bay during the 2021 HW revealed that most of the meadow darkening took place in the upper intertidal area, where plants were emerged for more than 13 h per day, while no significant darkening was observed in the lower intertidal zone. This contrasted with the experiment, in which seagrasses were exposed to a symmetric tidal cycle, spending equal amounts of time submerged and exposed to air. However, in the field, this configuration occurs only in meadows located at mean sea level. Thus, under the same atmospheric temperatures, bathymetry, and therefore exposure times will modulate the stress effects observed, as seagrasses located lower in the intertidal may be more resistant to HWs than those in the upper fringes. Field observations further revealed that leaf detachment began after the heatwave, causing an apparent decline in seagrass density at the upper intertidal. *Zostera noltii*, as a species inhabiting the intertidal zone and regularly exposed to air, has developed adaptations to minimize hydric stress, such as its narrow leaves, which help reduce water loss during air exposure periods (Cabaço et al., 2009). Nonetheless, if plants at the upper intertidal are exposed to intense heating and irradiance for

Fig. 12. Sentinel-2 true-colour composition of the seagrass meadow of Quiberon, South Brittany, France, Before (A; 1st of September 2021), During (B; 6th of September 2021) and After (C; 8th of October 2021) the HW and SHSI applied to the same Sentinel-2 images Before (D), During (E) and After (F) the HW.

Fig. 13. Relationship between the Seagrass Heat Shock Index (SHSI) and daily emersion time before (A) and during (B) the heatwave event. Each faded dot in panels (A) and (B) represents a single pixel. (C) Sentinel-2 true-colour composition acquired on 6 September 2021, during the heatwave. Red polygons indicate areas exposed to air for more than 13 h 19 min per day. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

prolonged periods, these mechanisms may not be able to prevent degradation of photosynthetic pigments, decreases in photosynthetic capacity and tissue degradation.

During the HW, Sentinel-2 imagery indicated that impacted seagrass patches (i.e., areas exhibiting seagrass darkening) experienced a sharp decline in NDVI. Moreover, the Sentinel-2 image acquired one month after the HW showed that the NDVI of impacted seagrass patches had not recovered to its initial level (Fig. 9B). NDVI is commonly used as a proxy for seagrass cover (Davies et al., 2024a; Zoffoli et al., 2020), with high NDVI associated with greater seagrass coverage and low NDVI indicating reduced cover. Our findings demonstrate that heatwaves altered the spectral signature of seagrasses, causing a decrease in NDVI—and consequently, in the satellite-derived estimate of seagrass cover—while the actual coverage observed in the field remained stable (see Fig. 6).

This discrepancy underscores a potential limitation of remote sensing in accurately capturing true seagrass cover during stress events. We demonstrate that such bias could be corrected by the combined analysis of both NDVI and SHSI indices, as proxies of seagrass cover and heatwave impact.

One month after the heatwave, the SHSI in impacted QPs recovered to similar values to those of the unimpacted ones. Moreover, Sentinel-2 images revealed a partial recovery in areas of the mid to low intertidal, as shown by their return to green colour. These results suggest a resilience capacity of *Z. noltii* after thermal disturbance. *Z. noltii* is a dynamic, fast-growing coloniser species (Roca et al., 2016), with fast leaf turnover times and growth rates (Borum et al., 2004) and fast rhizome elongation rates (Duarte, 1991). The return to green colour in some parts of the meadow after recovery might be due to new leaf growth, which was

likely sustained by the energy reserves of the surviving below-ground biomass (Hemminga, 1998).

Although Sentinel-2 imagery provides valuable coverage and spectral information for large-scale monitoring, its 10 m spatial resolution limits the ability to detect small or fragmented patches of heat-impacted seagrass, particularly in heterogeneous intertidal environments. In addition, the study of intertidal meadows using remote sensing techniques is constrained by environmental conditions at the time of image acquisition: the tide must be low enough to expose the seagrass canopy, and the scene must be free of clouds and haze. These two requirements substantially reduce the number of usable images and can limit temporal continuity during key events such as heatwaves. As a result, fine-scale degradation occurring at the patch or shoot level may remain undetected, leading to an underestimation of localised impacts.

Nevertheless, the consistency of Sentinel-2 data and its high revisit frequency make it a powerful tool for long-term, regional monitoring of seagrass responses to climate extremes. Combining Sentinel-2 with very-high-resolution sensors—such as multispectral drones or commercial satellites like WorldView or Pleiades-Neo—could improve the detection of early or spatially limited stress signals and provide a multi-scale monitoring framework for conservation and management applications.

4.3. Ecological implications of heatwaves impact on *Zostera noltii*

In the present study, we observed that heatwave-driven thermal stress changed the spectral reflectance of *Z. noltii* leaves, indicating photosynthetic pigments degradation, with potential negative consequences on health, growth, and survival of the above-ground biomass. In this sense, previous experiments on the effects of warming on *Z. noltii* have shown contrasting results, depending on the duration and intensity of heating. In some cases, there were no significant changes in photosynthetic performance or survival under short-term moderate stress (Franssen et al., 2014), or under gradual temperature increases (Román et al., 2022). By contrast, studies focused on extreme temperature events have evidenced decreases in photosynthetic performance and leaf tissue integrity (Massa et al., 2009; Román et al., 2023). Therefore, our findings, together with previous research, suggest that *Z. noltii* meadows at the upper intertidal could be a vulnerable under future global warming scenarios, where heatwaves will be more frequent and intense (Climate Change (IPCC), I.P., 2023; Stillman, 2019).

The observed leaf tissue degradation, both in the laboratory experiment and the field, can eventually result in decreases in meadow density and cover under recurrent heatwaves. Such darkening and loss of photosynthetic capacity at the leaf scale may ultimately translate into spatial fragmentation of meadows, as observed after major MHW events (Taylor et al., 2025). Incorporating fragmentation metrics alongside optical indicators like SHSI could thus improve assessments of seagrass vulnerability and recovery trajectories. This decline could have a cascading effect on species that rely on the provision of refuge and/or food by the seagrass canopy (Zoffoli et al., 2023). Commercially important fish and shellfish populations that rely on seagrass for sustenance and refuge could also be impacted, with negative consequences on local fisheries' productivity and the livelihoods of coastal communities (Unsworth and Cullen-Unsworth, 2014). Furthermore, as seagrass meadows decline, their capacity to act as a blue carbon sink—critical for climate mitigation—could diminish, contributing to increased atmospheric carbon levels (Armitage and Fourqurean, 2016; Samper-Villarreal et al., 2020). Moreover, the sediment stabilisation and wave attenuation could be hampered, ultimately increasing the risk of coastal erosion (Calleja et al., 2007; Folmer et al., 2012; Gacia et al., 1999).

Heatwaves rarely occur in isolation, and their ecological impact on seagrass meadows is likely to be amplified by interactions with other chronic stressors such as eutrophication, grazing pressure, and tidal exposure dynamics. Nutrient enrichment and eutrophication, for example, have been shown to synergistically worsen the effects of elevated temperatures—reducing photosynthetic efficiency and

accelerating stress-induced decline (Dias et al., 2025). Similarly, warming may foster epiphyte proliferation; under extreme temperatures, grazers may fail to control epiphyte growth, intensifying shading and delaying recovery (Lawrence and Bolton, 2023). In intertidal zones, tidal exposure modulates both desiccation and heat stress, meaning meadows in higher intertidal positions may suffer more aerial heat damage, while those in lower zones may face intense MHWs. These interactive processes emphasise that heat stress acts as a compounding driver, potentially pushing already pressured meadows beyond their physiological thresholds. The combined influence of local and global stressors is also evident in recovery dynamics: when other stressors co-occur, seagrass resilience and regrowth rates are often constrained (Smulders et al., 2025).

5. Conclusion

This study provides an integrated laboratory-to-satellite assessment of the effects of marine and atmospheric heatwaves on the reflectance of the intertidal seagrass *Zostera noltii*. By combining controlled experiments with multispectral satellite observations, we demonstrated that heat stress leads to consistent spectral changes associated with leaf darkening, pigment degradation, and reduced photosynthetic efficiency. The Seagrass Heat Shock Index (SHSI) developed here proved to be a sensitive and robust metric for detecting early heatwave-induced stress both in controlled and natural conditions. Its compatibility with Sentinel-2 spectral bands highlights its applicability for large-scale, repeatable, and operational monitoring of intertidal seagrass ecosystems.

Beyond its methodological contribution, this work enhances our understanding of how intertidal seagrasses respond to short-term thermal extremes and how these events can be captured using remote sensing. The validation performed in an independent site confirmed the transferability of the SHSI and its potential for integration into existing seagrass monitoring frameworks.

Nevertheless, several limitations must be acknowledged. Laboratory conditions, while allowing precise temperature control, cannot fully reproduce the complex interactions of field environments, such as hydrodynamics, light variability, and biological interactions. Similarly, the spatial resolution of Sentinel-2 (10 m) constrains the detection of small or mixed patches and may underestimate fine-scale impacts. Future work should therefore combine the SHSI with higher-resolution sensors and in situ spectral measurements to improve local-scale detection and validation.

Overall, this research provides a novel methodological pathway for quantifying and spatially evaluating the effects of heatwaves on intertidal vegetation, bridging laboratory experimentation and satellite monitoring. The SHSI represents a valuable tool for early detection of seagrass thermal stress, offering direct applications for ecosystem management, conservation planning, and climate resilience assessments. Continued development of this approach, particularly across species, regions, and seasons, will be key to advancing our predictive capacity and supporting adaptive management of coastal ecosystems under increasing climate extremes.

Founding

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Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Bede Ffinian Rowe Davies:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Philippe Rosa:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Augustin Debly:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Maria Laura Zoffoli:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Anne-Laure Barillé:** Data curation, Conceptualization. **Nicolas Harin:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Marta Román:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Jimmy de Fouw:** Data curation, Validation, Writing – review & editing. **Pierre Gernez:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Laurent Barillé:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Temperatures of the experiment

On average, in situ temperatures were 3 ± 3.2 °C higher than those recorded by Meteo France (Fig. A1). Additionally, temperatures recorded by Météo-France were more stable than those from the in situ sensors, likely due to the sheltered and shaded location of the M^to-France equipment. This difference was used to adjust heatwave temperatures measured by M^to-France to better reflect the conditions experienced by the seagrasses.

Fig. A1. Comparison of daily maximum temperatures in August measured using an in-situ sensor (blue) and retrieved from Météo-France (orange). The solid line in the middle of the boxplot represents the median, the two ends of the box represent the 25th and 75th percentiles, and the whiskers represent values that are no more than 1.5 times the interquartile range.

Appendix B. Outputs of GLMM

Table B1

Outputs of the Generalised Linear model assessing the relationship between time (days) and the relative change to the control of different vegetation indices (Fig. 8, Second Derivative, NDVI, GLI, and SHSI). Each index has two terms: Intercept and Slope. The Intercept represents the expected value of the index at the reference time point (e.g., day 0), while the Slope quantifies the effect of time, indicating how the index changes per unit increase in days. The Estimate represents the posterior mean of the regression coefficient, while Std. Error indicates its standard deviation. The Lower 95% CI and Upper 95% CI define the 95% credible interval, showing the range within which the true parameter is expected to fall with 95% probability. The Rhat statistic assesses model convergence (values close to 1 indicate proper convergence). Bulk_ESS and Tail_ESS denote the effective sample sizes for bulk estimation and tail uncertainty, respectively, reflecting the reliability of the posterior estimates.

Index	Term	Estimate	Std.Error	Lower 95% CI	Upper 95% CI	Rhat	Bulk_ESS	Tail_ESS
Second Derivative	Intercept	0.54	0.35	-0.21	1.25	1	5043.77	5181.38
	Slope	-0.41	0.03	-0.48	-0.35	1	32,534.18	13,213.4
NDVI	Intercept	0.11	0.13	-0.14	0.36	1	3717.38	2202.34
	Slope	-0.14	0.02	-0.17	-0.10	1	24,262.64	11,825.4
GLI	Intercept	0.22	0.29	-0.35	0.82	1	3827.11	3191.25
	Slope	-0.26	0.03	-0.32	-0.20	1	28,556.33	12,646.6
SHSI	Intercept	-1.34	0.40	-2.16	-0.48	1	6452.14	5210.97
	Slope	1.00	0.10	0.79	1.20	1	11,415.09	7365.45

Appendix C. Outputs of GAM

Table C1

Outputs of the Generalised Additive Model (GAM) assessing the relationship between emersion time per day (hours) and the SHSI (Fig. 13) during the heatwave event. The Intercept represents the expected SHSI value at the reference level of emersion time. The Estimate indicates the mean effect, with its Standard Error quantifying variability. The t-value and p-value assess statistical significance. The smooth term captures the nonlinear effect of emersion time, where the effective degrees of freedom (edf) reflect the function's complexity. The F-value and p-value evaluate the significance of this effect. Model fit is described by the adjusted R², deviance explained, and Generalized Cross-Validation (GCV) score, while N represents the sample size.

Component	Term	Estimate	Std Error	t-value	p-value	
A. parametric coefficients	(Intercept)	0.011	0.000	50.596	<0.0001	***
Component	Term	edf	Ref. df	F-value	p-value	
B. smooth terms	s(emersion_per_day)	2.999	3.000	1787.479	<0.0001	***

Signif. codes: 0 ≤ '****' < 0.001 < '***' < 0.01 < '**' < 0.05
Adjusted R-squared: 0.448, Deviance explained: 0.448
GCV: 0.000295, Scale est.: 0.000295, N: 6609

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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